

Collaborative bottom-up Trust Missions: A long-term strategy with and for people and Nature

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Both the European Union (EU) and the United Nations (UN) recognize that a healthy environment is essential for sustainable development. The central relevance of a healthy and resilient Ocean is further remarked by the two largest international programs in Ocean Sciences, the EU Ocean Mission Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030 and the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development. These top-down programs mainly focus on technical remediation and adaptation actions to reconcile a healthy environment with economic growth and development. However, the disappointing current regional and global development statistics evidence a need of prioritizing qualitative overall development over quantitative economic growth. Here we propose that the strategy towards overall development should rely on bottom-up programs that support the participation of people in communities that prime individual and collective happiness in harmony with Nature. We review how the UN and the EU have incorporated citizen engagement in their sustainability programs and conclude that there is an urgent need to create collaborative Trust (hope and care) Missions, empowering the citizens and communities to search and implement bottom-up preventive and transformative environmental actions. The current technical missions focus on short- or mid-term economic growth, while the proposed Trust Missions would represent a

long-term investment with and for people and Nature. The challenge is to prioritize individual, collective and societal development for the present and future generations, via the support and empowerment of bottom-up movements. In these times of social, environmental and climatic crises, upholding individuals and communities is likely the best strategy not only towards a healthy and resilient socio-economic system, but also to frame a society that values non-cognitive personal and collective development as much as knowledge and physical wellbeing.

Following its creation in 1945, the United Nations (UN) set its initial goals at safeguarding peace, protecting human rights, and establishing the framework for international justice and social progress. Eighty years later, the UN has widely expanded its objectives by pointing to 29 major evolving issues that deserve urgent international attention¹. Only two of these current goals are directly related to the environment – oceans and the law of the sea, and climate change – but it is unquestionable that many of the other major UN priorities, from food and poverty to water and health, are intimately linked to a healthy environment. The current UN motto² – *Peace, dignity and equality on a healthy planet* – indeed sends a very clear message that the planetary crises are deeply connected to the crystal-clear fact that we are overexploiting our planet³⁻⁷.

In the early 1990s, the UN began focusing on how true social development demands environmental sustainability. At the UN Conference on Environment and Development (Earth Summit, 1992), the UN General Assembly (UNGA) launched the Agenda 21 with the central objective of achieving global sustainable development (SD) by the year 2000, through a dozen environmental topics, among them the protection of oceans, seas and coastal regions (Fig. 1). However, slow effective progress was evidenced in the two subsequent UN conferences on SD, the Earth Summit 2002 and the Earth Summit 2012. Nevertheless, this last summit produced the document *The Future we Want*⁸, with precise phases towards implementing a global sustainability strategy. It also marked the start of a process that led to the 2015 UN Sustainable Development Summit, where the UNGA approved the resolution *Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development* (Agenda 2030) with 17 global Sustainable Development Goals⁹⁻¹² (SDGs; Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Time evolution of the major international sustainability programs that have the Ocean at their core. The introductory section of this article sets the historical context that in 2015 led to the UN SDGs while the remaining sections explore the connections between the UN and EU programs on SD, with emphasis on those related to the Ocean. In bold letters those events that are most connected with citizen engagement; the GA resolution on Harmony with Nature is italicized to emphasize its strong symbolism. UNOC: UN Ocean Conference; UNODC: UN Ocean Decade Conference.

The SDGs form the basis for a resilient and inclusive pathway to reach the economic, social and environmental dimensions of development, recognizing the interconnection of the individual and social crises with the environmental and climatic crises. The 29 UN compelling global issues¹ can be summarized as global crises in equity – which involve all sort of human egoisms and exploitations of people and Nature, ranging from poverty to wars – and in individual-

community happiness – which reach well beyond physical wellbeing as it includes aspects such as eco-anxiety^{13,14} and lack of personal peace (*solastalgia*)¹⁵. Nevertheless, the environmental and climatic crises are possibly the clearest expression of our lack of harmony with Nature, our excesses in using rather than our will of being part of planet Earth.

The goal of this article is to analyze how the UN and EU strategies on scientific research are evolving in terms of promoting and supporting citizen engagement with the Ocean. We start reviewing the ideas behind economic growth and overall development in the frame of the SDGs and examine how the EU's plan to become a world leader in environmental sustainability. We then explore how the UN has incorporated ocean sciences and citizen engagement to reach the SDGs and how the Ocean is articulated within Horizon Europe – the principal EU research funding program – and further look at the relevance and role of citizen engagement in these processes. We end by arguing that the mobilization and engagement of individuals, organizations and networks is the only pathway for a true economic, societal and environmental transformation, and that this has to be actively supported through collaborative bottom-up *Trust Missions*.

Harmony with Nature and the Green Deal

Remarkably, but possibly much less known than the SDGs, in 2009 the UNGA acknowledged that “*in order to achieve a just balance among the economic, social, and environmental needs of present and future generations, it is necessary to promote harmony with Nature and the Earth*” and further recognized “*the interdependence that exists among human beings, other living beings and the planet we all inhabit*”, designating April 22 as the International Mother Earth Day¹⁶⁻¹⁸. In these 15 years since this declaration, a total of 12 resolutions on Harmony with Nature have been adopted by the UNGA, often in the form of dialogues, addressing a wide variety of themes that include science and education, SD, biodiversity, Earth jurisprudence, ethical economy and consumption patterns, poverty eradication and climate justice, human health and the engagement of citizens and societies. In all cases, the focus has been on social participation with a non-anthropocentric vision of Nature, promoting an Earth-centered rather than a people-centered implementation of the SDGs agenda.

The UN movement on Harmony with Nature, however, has had little impact on governmental policies and practices. Sustainability is still viewed from a utilitarian, paternalistic and anthropic perspective, driving for a healthy Earth system rather than searching for an individual and collective sense of pertinence to Mother Earth. The economic system is based on immediacy earnings with a utilitarian view of Nature, and happiness is promoted from the perspective of *having* rather than *being*¹⁹, which drives us away from the natural harmonic rhythms of Nature (see section on Growth and Economy in the Supplementary Materials). The widespread use of Gross Domestic Product (GDP)²⁰ as a measure of countries' relative development or progress is a good example of this. GDP is a purely quantitative measure of the cash value of economic output, excluding anything more qualitative such as environmental health, wellbeing and happiness. The bleeding of planet Earth drives climate change and ecosystem degradation, largely impacting the less-developed and most-vulnerable populations, and mortgaging the wellbeing of the future generations... but we still appear to rely on unknown bioengineering solutions to the environmental and climatic crises, influencing that the Earth's overexploitation not only continues but rather increases.

Since the 1960's, social-environmental movements around the globe have prompted governments to move away from nonrenewable energy sources, initially out of fear of nuclear

power and more recently in response to climate change²¹. However, the initial public investments towards renewable energy sources (and nuclear in the case of France) were driven by economic necessity, to face the soaring oil and gas prices caused by the 1970's energy crisis and, recently, by the Russia-Ukraine war. The last decade has witnessed an exponential growth of these grassroots movements – as evidenced by the worldwide manifestations, specially of young people, during the Conferences of the Parties – denouncing the overexploiting of the Earth resources by a minority. This loud call for a more harmonious relation with Nature should be envisioned by governments not only as a pressing social imperative but also as an extraordinary opportunity for transformative individual and societal wellbeing.

These grassroots movements, and the green political parties that share some of their views, prompted the EU into a bloc strategy to tackle climate change, biodiversity loss and pollution – the 2020 Agenda²² towards a circular and carbon-neutral economy by 2050 – known as the Green Deal (Fig. 1). The citizen-engaged components of the Green Deal, and particularly its research and innovation Horizon Europe program, represent major steps towards more participatory and democratic governance. For example, Horizon Europe actively funds several projects that implement deliberative democratic activities such as citizen and stakeholder assemblies (e.g. PREP4BLUE²³), or that engage towards increasing social inclusion and diversity in European ocean sciences and policies (e.g. TIDAL ArtS²⁴). This represents a real possibility for integrating the enthusiasm and innovation of civil movements into the social transformative process, setting the true interests of people – not those determined by the economic interests of a minority – at the center of the EU agenda. Horizon Europe is indeed a unique opportunity for placing Harmony with Nature as the leading vision towards a transformative change in Europe, which could become a worldwide model.

The Ocean in the UN and EU development strategies

The SDGs are outlined in terms of targets, each with one or more specific indicators of progress, but their implementation relies largely on the committed work of UN agencies, sustained by the member states through their voluntary contributions. As a result, resources for an international operational plan that goes beyond promoting the engagement of all stakeholders, from citizens to governments, are very limited. Regarding the health of the Ocean, the logistics relies on the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of the UN Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO)²⁵, founded in 1960 and composed of 150 member states. The IOC promotes the advancement of marine sciences towards SD through international cooperation and capacity development in ocean monitoring, management, research and literacy. In particular, the IOC contributes to and reports on SGD 14 (Life below water: Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for SD).

Building on meetings that began in 2017, the IOC launched the Decade of Ocean Sciences for Sustainable Development (hereafter Ocean Decade), to run between 2021 and 2030 (Fig. 1). The Ocean Decade directly addresses SDG 14²⁶ but extends to all other SDGs because of the economic, social and environmental relevance of the Ocean for all people on Earth. Under the motto *“The science we need for the Ocean we want”*, the Ocean Decade aims to be a bottom-up *“revolution to unlock innovative science solutions”* towards SD. This ambition is most apparent in the implementation of the Decade's Challenges 9 (Skills, knowledge, technology and participatory decision-making for all) and 10 (Restoring society's relationship with the ocean)^{27,28}.

Challenge 9 explicitly calls for participation in science and governance, and Challenge 10 seeks to integrate non-academic knowledge into ocean science and investigation. The inclusive enlightenment foreseen in Challenge 10 is expressed in its main objective – *“to understand the values and services of the ocean for human well-being, culture and SD, and identify and overcome behavior barriers for changing humankind relation with the Ocean”*²⁸ – which is to be accomplished by incorporating qualitative sciences, such as arts and philosophy, as well as traditional and local knowledge, such as indigenous codesigned and integrative science²⁹. Both Challenges 9 and 10 are supported by the activities in thousands of Ocean Decade actions³⁰ around the globe – many of which are bottom up and participatory in essence.

Complementary to the Ocean Decade bottom-up strategy, the UN has also organized three high-level top-down Ocean Conferences (2017, 2022 and one to be held in Nice in June 2025)³¹, with the participation of high-level representatives of national government and other relevant stakeholders. These Conferences aim to showcase progress towards reaching the SDG 14, adopting intergovernmental declarations that list voluntary national commitments towards the conservation and sustainable use of the Ocean. France, co-host country of the third UN Ocean Conference in 2025, has proposed to add three special events in order to involve the ocean community and stakeholders at large: the One Ocean Science Congress, the Blue Economy and Finance Forum, and the Ocean Rise and Coastal Resilience Coalition Summit³².

The EU Green Deal – launched in December 2019, approved in January 2020, and largely implemented throughout 2020 and 2021^{33,34} – is set to transform the EU economy and society towards climate-neutrality by 2050, bringing Europe as the first continent to achieve so. The Green Deal strategy promotes, supports, and enforces sustainable transport, clean-technology manufacturing, clean energy sources, renovated and efficient homes, the restoration of natural ecosystems, and the establishment of international commitments towards climate neutrality. To deploy the Green Deal strategy, the EU will mobilize no less than €1 trillion, equivalent to 30% of its multiannual budget (2021-2028), which includes one-third of the €1.8 trillion NextGenerationEU Recovery Plan³⁵. The implementation is based on many interconnected programs, including the preservation and regeneration of Nature (biodiversity strategy), the development of environmental policies (environmental action program), as well as action plans (APs) for unpolluted air, water and soil (zero pollution AP) and sustainable circular economy (circular economy AP). It also includes Horizon Europe, a research and innovation program designed to drive transformative change by developing and deploying the necessary scientific, societal and economic innovations, and engaging citizens in the process.

Horizon Europe has an indicative budget of about €95 billion³⁶⁻³⁹, supporting three pillars as well as a program to widen and strengthen research collaboration. The largest of these pillars is the one on excellent science, innovation, and global challenges and industrial competitiveness (GC&IC), with an estimated funding of some €55 billion, comprising six Clusters and five Missions (see section on The Ocean in the Horizon Europe Program in the Supplementary Materials.) Three of the GC&IC Clusters are directly related to environmental sustainability: Cluster 2 (Culture, Creativity and Inclusive Society), Cluster 5 (Climate, Energy and Mobility) and Cluster 6 (Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment). Additionally, three of the Missions directly connect to environmental sustainability: Adaptation to climate change, hereafter Mission Climate; Restore our Ocean

and waters by 2030, hereafter Mission Ocean; and Climate-neutral and smart cities, hereafter Mission Cities⁴⁰⁻⁴².

Social objectives are indeed present in the three Clusters and three Missions related with the environment, albeit with quite different emphases. In particular, Ocean research shows up in them all but naturally stands out in Mission Ocean. Table 1 provides a qualitative overview, based solely on the keywords found in the objectives and strategies in the implementation plans, showing how much these programs are connected to environmental protection and regeneration (both to Nature in general and the Ocean in particular) and how much they intend to engage citizens in this process. Remarkably, Cluster 6 and Mission Ocean are the only programs highly connected to both the environment and citizen participation but, as expected, only Mission Ocean is deeply driven to recover the health of the Ocean and waters. The total commitment for all five Missions during the 2021-2023 implementation period is €1.9 billion⁴³, but there is no exact budget set for each Mission. In particular, Mission Ocean launched calls for a total of €197.4 million for the 2023-2024 work program⁴⁴.

Table 1. Qualitative degree of connection with Nature, Ocean and citizen engagement, for EU Clusters and Missions related to environmental sustainability. The low, moderate and high levels respectively stand for not showing, marginally exposed or centrally present in the general and specific objectives or enablers.

Program	Nature	Ocean	Citizen engagement
Cluster 2 - Culture, Creativity and Inclusive Society	Moderate	Low	High
Cluster 5 - Climate, Energy and Mobility	Moderate	Low	Moderate
Cluster 6 - Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment	High	Low	High
Mission Climate - Adaptation to climate change	Moderate	Low	High
Mission Ocean - Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030	High	High	High
Mission Cities - 100 climate-neutral and smart-cities by 2030	Moderate	Low	Moderate

The UN Ocean Decade and the EU Mission Ocean and Waters

The health of the Ocean, the principal and essential component of the living Earth, is at stake⁶. The environmental and climatic crises are causing changes that are difficult to predict: the marine ecosystems are degrading, with a dramatic loss of biodiversity and resilience, and the Earth's thermodynamic state is likely approaching a threshold towards an unknown state of equilibrium. Prompted by this situation, the UN produced the Ocean Decade as part of the strategy to address SDG 14 on Life below water, and the EU launched Mission Ocean as part of the Horizon Europe research and innovation program under the Green Deal. Both the Mission Ocean and the Ocean Decade have shown substantial flexibility to evolve since their initial

conception, and they both appear to continue evolving to the observed deficiencies, the changing situations and the rising opportunities.

The Ocean Decade matured naturally during its conception and early stages. From the initial desideratum of seven outcomes linked to all 17 SDGs⁴⁵, the Decade is now mainly expressed in terms of 10 gross challenges⁴⁶, each of them to be attained through a sequence of three objectives via the establishment of actions (Fig. 2). The objectives are: to identify the knowledge required for SD and deliver the necessary ocean data and information; to build capacity and generate comprehensive interdisciplinary ocean knowledge; and to increase the use of this knowledge towards sustainable solutions. The actions are both top-down and bottom-up initiatives that include programs (from regional to international), projects, activities, all types of contributions and the establishment and/or participation in networks.

Figure 2. On the connection between the five Mission Ocean objectives/enablers and the 10 Ocean Decade challenges, illustrating that only one Mission enabler and two Decade challenges focus on citizen engagement.

The 2024 UN Ocean Decade Conference (UNODC)⁴⁷, held in Barcelona in April 2024, was an excellent forum to promote and network citizen and civil organizations within the Ocean Decade, evidencing the progress attained and setting the pace for many preparatory pre-, in- and post-conference meetings. One concrete outcome is the 10 Ocean Decade Vision 2030 White Papers (one per Decade outcome)⁴⁸, which contribute to the Ocean action panels prepared for the top-down 2025 UN Ocean Conference (UNOC)^{31,49}. The UNODC main event together with more than 100 bottom-up satellite events, mostly coordinated by citizen

organizations and networks, have confirmed the growing strength of networking within the global Ocean community.

Mission Ocean has also evolved substantially since the original 2018 ideas⁵⁰, becoming increasingly interdisciplinary and intersectoral, and continuously diversifying in both the strategies and the number and topics of the calls for proposals⁴². Currently there are also plans for cross-Mission calls, a natural consequence of the centrality of climate and environmental action in the Climate and Cities Missions. A distinctive feature in the formulation of Mission Ocean is that its three objectives (protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems, prevent and eliminate pollution, and make the blue economy carbon neutral and circular) are pursued through two enablers (Fig. 2). The first one is the digital twin of the Ocean – a virtual ocean and water knowledge system that builds on existing and planned infrastructures and services, aimed at monitoring and forecasting – a fairly concrete and knowledge-oriented tool. In contrast, the second-one is a ground-based collaborative and inclusive facilitator oriented at empowering society towards transformation, particularly to mobilize and interconnect people for the conservation and regeneration of the Ocean.

Citizen engagement within the Ocean Decade and Mission Ocean

Most people in the developed countries are aware of the reality of the environmental and climatic crises⁵¹, and even recognize that their ecological footprint often contributes to an unsustainable socio-economic pathway, yet they do not change their daily careless behavior. This lack of response to these crises reflects a major disconnection between knowledge and emotions, possibly combined with other feelings such as fatalism (nothing can be done), skeptic denial (the crises are false or exaggerated, because changes are difficult to appreciate at daily scales), selfishness (total lack of empathy towards vulnerable communities and future generations), or an inaccurate confidence that humankind can continue overexploiting the Earth because miraculous bioengineering solutions will appear. The truth is that transformative social changes can only be accomplished with the engagement of people, a responsibility that goes from small daily actions to multiplicative local-to-international committed networking.

Collaborative citizen engagement and networking are an important component of the Ocean Decade (Fig. 2). Outcome 7 (An inspiring and engaging Ocean, understood and valued in relation to human well-being and SD) and Challenge 10 point directly to the relevance of mobilizing citizens. However, supporting and engaging people requires funding, so the implementation plan of the Ocean Decade⁵² (hereafter Decade Plan) is largely dedicated to stakeholder engagement with the Ocean, proposing diverse measures to secure resources.

In practice, organizations get involved in the Ocean Decade mainly through leading or participating in a Decade action. While the success of the UNODC confirmed the interest of many worldwide bottom-up movements on the Ocean Decade, it also showed that the Decade has not yet been able to secure funding to support most of these groups. Currently, only three Decade Coordination Offices are being directly funded – one of them on Connecting people and Ocean – and a handful of Decade Collaborative Centers are hosted by international or regional institutions. Additionally, there are half a dozen regional planning groups, many national committees, and 55 Decade thematic programs³⁰. However, only five of these programs directly aim at promoting citizen engagement actions: Ocean literacy with all,

Decade of Ocean empathy, Ocean voices, Ocean cities network, and Cultural heritage framework. Organizations can also engage through the Ocean Decade Network platform⁵³, a virtual tool that allows exploring and connecting with a limited number (12) of existing communities of practices (CoPs), although none centrally focused on citizen engagement.

Mission Ocean has also incorporated citizen engagement-mobilization as one of its key enablers, a singularity that is not found in any other Mission (Table 1). The implementation plan of Mission Ocean⁴² (hereafter Mission Plan) emphasizes that this transformative facilitator must address the following aspects: fill the knowledge-emotional gap; promote the EU global leadership in Ocean & waters sustainability and governance; develop and pilot frameworks and processes; test and apply deliberative democracy mechanisms and social innovation practices; and promote ocean literacy, education and training, and citizen science. The Mission Plan explicitly recognizes that people too often lack responsibility with sustainability in their daily actions, largely because of a knowledge-emotional disconnection, and emphasizes that citizens can be *agents of change*⁴².

An essential aspect of the citizen's connection with the Ocean is the extraordinary potential – physical, intellectual and emotional – that lays behind collective working. The Mission Plan recognizes that engaging with the Ocean is, above all, a synergistic process that runs in parallel with the creation and development of inclusive, participatory and democratic networks committed with the environment⁴². Promoting citizen connection implies *“mobilising and empowering citizens for the co-design and co-implementation of solutions”*. The citizen engagement enabler must *“facilitate broad ownership and education and co-design the transitions within the communities”* towards the Green Deal targets. The keyword is collaboration: the Mission *“will leverage social innovation throughout the co-design, co-development, co-implementation, and co-monitoring of solutions for sustainable use of the ocean and waters”*⁴².

The Mission Ocean Charter⁵⁴ also provides a tool for engaging private and public stakeholders. Any interested party can pledge *“to co-design, propose and implement policies, programs, projects or initiatives that will contribute to the restoration of our ocean and waters.”* By submitting their pledge, the organizations become part of the Mission community, opening up opportunities for collaboration and participation in Mission events.

Trust Missions

Despite the unquestionable relevance given to citizen engagement in Mission Ocean and the Ocean Decade, both programs focus primarily on the technical aspects of applied marine sciences. Transformative social science has much less weight, as reflected by the relatively low number of related challenges/objectives in the Decade/Mission. In the Ocean Decade, only one among seven outcomes – Outcome 7 on an inspiring and engaging Ocean – is related to citizen engagement; and only two out of 10 challenges address this topic: Challenge 10 on the relation of humanity with the ocean and Challenge 9 on knowledge and technology for all, the latter indirectly related through capacity building (Fig. 2). Regarding Mission Ocean, only one single enabler (public mobilization and engagement in the co-design and co-delivery of the solutions) out of three objectives and two enablers addresses the need to enhance the citizen commitment with the Ocean. The relatively low relevance of citizen engagement in the overall strategy of both programs is evidenced in the Decade Network and Ocean Charter platforms,

as there is no way for individual citizens to get involved. Both platforms do encourage organizations to submit actions but there is no funding channel.

The lack of effective and clear instruments to engage individuals and fund ocean-related civil organizations is a major constraint in the implementation of either Mission Ocean or the Ocean Decade. The shortage of resources to support grassroots movements, which is understandable in an Ocean Decade that is still trying to secure funding channels, is a handicap in the setup of truly transformative programs aimed at empowering civil organizations. Equally binding is that individuals have no clear path to get involved in either the Ocean Decade or Mission Ocean. Both weaknesses call for rethinking priorities in both the Decade and Mission Plans, finding and identifying direct and indirect channels for individuals to participate and organizations to get funded. They also point at the benefits of recognizing and supporting projects in Marine Social Sciences that can design and pilot innovative and transformative methods and strategies⁵⁵⁻⁵⁷.

The technical emphasis of the Mission Ocean and Ocean Decade programs is no surprise, it simply responds to the dominance of economic growth in the development concept (see section on Growth and Economy in the Supplementary Materials). In the case of Mission Ocean, this emphasis reflects the prominence of the green/blue and circular economic models in the Green Deal strategy, which does not renounce to economic growth. A similar priority shows up in development reports from either the Conferences of the Parties or various private stakeholders⁵⁸⁻⁶², yet with some notable exceptions⁶³. The truth is, however, that all these approaches have limited effectivity, as clearly shown by different climatic, environmental and social indicators: the substantial worldwide increase (+8.5%) and moderate EU decrease (-1.7%) of greenhouse emissions between 2015 and 2023^{64,65}; the progressive transgression of the planetary boundaries (critical levels in key global processes to ensure the maintenance of a stable and resilient Earth) between 2009 and 2023³⁻⁷; the uncertain evolution of poverty over the last three decades, with a global decrease thanks to valuable progress in China and India but with negative results in Latin America and especially Africa, and with over one-fifth of the European population at risk of poverty or social exclusion in 2023^{66,67}.

These figures point at the need for an urgent shift towards a new paradigm of SD: the promotion of overall qualitative development rather than quantitative economic growth through a sense of pertinence and harmony in Nature rather than with a utilitarian anthropic perspective. This implies moving from quantitative to qualitative, from economic growth to integrative development, effectively involving people and, if necessary, proposing and supporting specific measures for economic degrowth (see section on Growth and Economy in the Supplementary Materials).

To back this new paradigm, we propose that there should be two types of Missions: scientific-technical and collaborative. Current programs, with Mission Ocean and the Ocean Decade as good examples, focus mainly on the search for technical solutions. They start from a general idea, call it objective or challenge, and search for remediation (e.g. a clean non-contaminated ocean) or adaptation (e.g. a secure ocean) measures. The alternative is to support people in their search and participation in networks and CoPs that prime individual and collective happiness over economic growth, we may call them collaborative *Trust* Missions, a name that reflects both hope and care. In these Trust Missions, the citizens and communities would be

empowered to design, test and implement preventive measures (e.g. an Ocean that inspires harmony and collaboration) through networking and transformative bottom-up actions.

The scientific-technical mission is of short- or mid-term economic interest that prioritizes economic growth, while the Trust mission is a long-term investment for people and Nature that primes overall development. Certainly, well communicated science is a powerful enabler for curiosity, emotion and ultimately for people to care for Nature; however, this is a necessary but not sufficient condition: knowledge alone is hardly transformative as people responds to emotions^{68,69}. And technology has the power to largely improve human welfare, and planet Earth has reached a situation that does require remediation and adaptation measures, but it is unquestionable that the best science will not deliver effective solutions if humanity – each of us – does not end its excesses, even bioengineering solutions will only delay and exacerbate the problem. The challenge is to find the ways for filling the knowledge-emotional gap, as clearly recognized in the Mission Plan⁴².

How should these Trust Missions be framed? Given the complexity of the issues that have to be addressed – especially the climatic and environmental crises - what goals should be pursued? Complex problems require complex integrative solutions, they demand inclusive, collaborative and democratic processes in all phases, from the design to the implementation of strategies. This suggests that it is time to go back to the origins, to return to larger and more integrative views, possibly mirroring the evolution of applied sciences. From the holistic scientific knowledge held by great naturalists during the 19th and first half of the 20th century, in the second half of the 20th century science moved into an age of overspecialization that brought important technological advances but also led to isolation and a consequent loss of scientific creativity and innovation. Major exceptions, such as the development of antibiotics and the structure of DNA⁷⁰, indeed corresponded to collaborative interdisciplinary work addressing complex questions. Conversely, interdisciplinary teams have emerged in the last decades to undertake complex problems – with clear successful examples in fields such as biophysics and complex systems⁷¹.

Building on these experiences, Trust Missions could be framed around the central crises of our time, turning them into opportunities. Global crises – in particular the environmental and climatic crises – would become naturally interlinked Trust Missions, the most urgent and compelling integrative and transversal programs that require an intersectoral and interdisciplinary response from all actors.

In order to address the environmental or climatic crises, the Earth system cannot be split into lithosphere, hydrosphere, atmosphere, cryosphere and biosphere, as all these components are intrinsically connected, and neither makes sense to ask citizens to engage with one of these five components and neglect the others. Hence, the Trust Missions should also be Earth-system oriented, possibly allowing some structuring into different chapters for practical reasons but never from a conceptual perspective, e.g. the citizen engaging strategies in a coastal town will likely differ from those in a rural inland community but the goals are the same. Figure 3 illustrates, as an example, the fundamental difference between Mission Ocean and a Trust Mission focused on climate and seaside communities.

Figure 3. (Top) Mission Ocean, as an example of a technical mission: the central green+blue circle represents the general and thematic objectives, encircled by a yellow ring that represents their enablers; these are encircled by technical projects-outputs (gray ring) and the target basins (outer orange ring); the outward-going arrows representing technical and scientific methods and tools developed to carry out the projects and obtain the products. (Bottom) The Climate-Ocean Trust mission: the central green circle represents the grand (integrative) climate challenge, encircled by a blue ring with citizen engagement objectives and a yellow ring for mobilization strategies; these are encircled by the social actors (gray ring) and the target basins (outer orange ring); the inward arrows represent the co-creation/co-design of collaborative inclusive and democratic methods to reach the citizen engagement objectives.

Agents of change

We are all agents of change. Each of our apparently tiny daily sustainability actions is significant, they all are the necessary building blocks not only to reduce our ecological footprint but, most important, to spread thoughts and actions towards SD. But our personal evolution, both in terms of inner meditation and outer action, is tightly linked with the evolution of our community. This is a progressive multi-level feedback process: as I evolve and have the will and support to express and share this evolution then the community will advance and, in turn, I will feed from the increasing maturity of the community and each of its members. And the same feedback evolving process applies between the communities and the entire society, as well as between national societies and supra-national unions such as the EU and the UN.

This process between individuals and the community may often require intermediate structures. As communities get larger, something characteristic of neighborhoods in large cities, individuals usually interact with the community through fairly simple social structures that work for the common wellbeing, such as non-profit civil associations of multiple kinds. Further networking can be established among associations with similar objectives, and the resulting networks can link with other networks that have different but related objectives, creating an interdisciplinary and often intersectoral CoP.

The wonderful thing is that networking and bottom-up action is a reality. It is already happening in many places without public support, driven by the selfless and empathetic character of many people who believe that they can become agents of change in the face of the global crises, people who think globally and act locally. Indeed, pilot actions to engage and mobilize citizens⁷² have proven that very small investment can lead to significant transformative actions. This is a clear and loud message: investing in citizen mobilization and engagement is an outstanding opportunity to obtain maximum SD results at very low cost. All public stakeholders should take very good note of this opportunity and set the mechanisms to support: individuals to evolve not only cognitively through capacity building and ocean literacy, but specially in positive values and emotions through sensory-artistic experiences; associations to attract motivated individuals, carry out their non-profit community service, and network with other civil entities; and networks to explore synergies and develop positive dynamics that lead to intersectoral CoPs.

The challenge for public stakeholders is to think not in terms of immediate economic return but rather in terms of individual, collective and societal development – for the present and future generations – and to develop the right mechanisms to materialize the transition towards a sustainable society with and for people and Nature. Here we propose that these mechanisms rely on a profound societal transformation and that this can only be accomplished via bottom-up movements, which should be supported by Trust-type missions that engage and mobilize citizens towards addressing global crises such as the climatic and environmental ones. By fully harnessing the power of collaborative work for overall development, the Trust Missions would identify, design and support effective actions and engaging ways to advance and spread sustainable attitudes.

In these times of social, environmental and climatic crises – and of personal crisis in much of the developed world⁷³ – supporting individuals and communities is likely the best strategy not only for a healthy, resilient, productive and fair socio-economic system, but especially to embrace Harmony with Nature. Trust Missions can have an extraordinary transformative value at relatively low cost, investing in a society that highly regards knowledge and physical wellbeing but equally treasures non-cognitive personal and collective development in values such as peace, empathy, sensibility, joy, happiness and love. We encourage the EU, as a global leader in sustainability, to prime this bottom-up Trust approach in shaping the Green Deal, its Horizon Europe research and innovation program, and the upcoming European Oceans Pact⁷⁴.

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Supplementary Materials for

Collaborative bottom-up Trust Missions: A long-term strategy with and for people and Nature

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List of Acronyms

CoP	community of practice
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GC&IC	Global challenges and industrial competitiveness
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
IOC	Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission
Mission Cities	EU Mission 100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030
Mission Climate	EU Mission Climate Change Adaptation
Mission Ocean	EU Mission Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2023
Ocean Decade	UN Decade of Ocean Sciences for Sustainable Development
SD	sustainable development
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
UN	United Nations
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
UNGA	United Nations General Assembly
UNOC	United Nations Ocean Conference
UNODC	United Nations Ocean Decade Conference

Growth versus Development

During the last three decades, the United Nations (UN) has endorsed the need for a more equitable and sustainable future, unfolded in 2015 through the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and the EU turned in 2020 the world leader in sustainability through its Green Deal program. The challenge is how to place equity and sustainability in action, with the omnipresent conditioning of immediate economic growth brought about by powerful stakeholders that nevertheless often lack social legitimacy.

The growth-development issue undoubtedly lays behind every international strategic proposal such as the SDGs and the Green Deal. In biology, growth refers to biological and physical traits while development relates to functional and behavioral changes, with the biophysical characteristics being only one among many forcing that set the actual development. In the social and economic sciences, economic growth represents an increase in the production of goods and services, commonly measured in terms of Gross Domestic Product (GDP). In contrast, development is a much more complex issue as it does not relate to an average economy but is rather an overall view of human wellbeing, which incorporates the social-environmental dimensions and considers the individual and community economic, cultural and health anomalies. The degree of environmental health-degradation and citizen engagement-disengagement is not assessed by the economic growth but should certainly be part of any overall assessment of development.

Nowadays, growth and development must necessarily be viewed from the perspective of an overexploited planet^{1,2}, with positive demographic increase still to remain until the end of this century (225% increase in the period 1950-2023; 2.5% increase in 2020-2023)³. Under these conditions, it may be argued that global economic growth is impossible, as it would eventually lead to the breakdown of the entire system. In contrast, overall development is entirely

possible, as a decline in economic growth may be by far compensated by an increase in social and environmental benefits, while ensuring the continued availability of natural capital and ecosystemic services to future generations⁴⁻⁶. The question of how such a SD can be maintained has been at the core of very diverse economic models – including circular economy, blue and green economy, and degrowth⁷.

Circular models aim to minimize resources and extend the lifetime of products and materials through the long-term design and use of existing products, as well as by sharing materials and recycling them back to the production chain⁸. Blue and green models are based on technological improvements (e.g. renewable energies) that reconcile growth with planetary sustainability, but this is conditioned by physical constraints, in particular the limited availability of the raw materials required for the transition. Degrowth models describe a pathway to a steady-state economy through downscaling production and consumption, priming increased individual and social wellbeing in a healthy and resilient environment⁹⁻¹³.

Despite the differences between the above sustainability models – in particular, the circular and blue/green models sustain that growth and development are still compatible while the degrowth model advocates zero growth – it is clear that they all share many key aspects. Possibly the central difficulty lies in the practical implementation of the model so as to make SD a reality.

The Ocean in the Horizon Europe Program

Horizon Europe¹⁴ is the research and innovation program of the EU Green Deal, supporting three pillars – excellent science, innovation, and global challenges and industrial competitiveness (GC&IC) – as well as a program to widen and strengthen research collaboration. The largest of these pillars is GC&IC, comprising six Clusters (health; culture, creativity and inclusive societies; civil security for society; digital industry and space; climate, energy and mobility; food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment) and five Missions¹⁵ (adaptation to climate change; cancer; restore our Ocean and waters; climate-neutral and smart cities; soil deal for Europe).

Three Clusters in the GC&IC pillar are directly related to environmental sustainability:

- Cluster 2 (Culture, Creativity and Inclusive Society)¹⁶ mobilizes multidisciplinary expertise to strengthen European democratic values by: enhancing democratic governance and citizen participation; safeguarding and promoting cultural heritage; promoting multifaceted social, economic, technological and cultural transformations that contribute to inclusion and growth; understanding contemporary transformations of society, economy, politics and culture; providing evidence-based policy options for a socially just and inclusive Green and digital transition and recovery in the EU.
- Cluster 5 (Climate, Energy and Mobility)¹⁷ supports the provision of knowledge to fight climate change by: better understanding its causes, evolution, risks, impacts and opportunities; producing a twin green and digital transformation of the economy, industry and society towards climate neutrality while boosting their competitiveness, resilience and benefits for citizens and society; making the energy and transport sectors more climate and environment-friendly, more efficient and competitive, smarter, safer and more resilient.

- Cluster 6 (Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment)¹⁸ offers opportunities towards a healthy environment and food and nutrition security by: strengthening and balancing environmental, social and economic goals; setting human economic activities on a path towards sustainability; producing transformative changes that reduce environmental degradation, reverse the decline of biodiversity and better manage natural resources; strengthening the EU autonomy, particularly in the energy and food sectors through knowledge, innovation and digitalization; steering and accelerating the transition to a low carbon, resource efficient circular economy and sustainable bioeconomy.

Additionally, three of the GC&IC Missions are directly connect to environmental sustainability:

- Adaptation to climate change, hereafter Mission Climate¹⁹, is to foster at least 150 climate resilient regions and communities by 2030: preparing and planning regions and communities for climate resilience; accelerating the safe transformations of regions and communities towards climate resilience; and demonstrating systemic transformations to climate resilience across regions and communities.
- Restore our Ocean and waters by 2030, hereafter Mission Ocean²⁰, will contribute to restore the hydrosphere: protecting and restoring marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity; preventing and eliminating pollution in the Ocean, seas and waters; and creating a carbon-neutral and circular sustainable blue economy. Two enablers will support these objectives: the implementation of a digital knowledge and monitoring system for the Ocean and waters, and a participatory governance based on public mobilization and engagement.
- Climate-neutral and smart cities, hereafter Mission Cities²¹, is to deliver at least 100 European climate-neutral and smart cities by 2030 and to act as experimentation and innovation hubs for to turn all European cities climate-neutral by 2050: the following areas will be addressed: climate research and innovation; pilot projects to scale-up and replicate solutions; synergies and complementarities; international networks for good practice and joint actions; development of innovative administrative, financial and policy capacity; monitoring progress towards climate neutrality; public assistance and private investment.

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